

Integration of NeutroAlgebra and Neutrosophic 2-Tuple Linguistic Likert Scales for Feasibility Assessment in Industrial Projects

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Abstract. The study addresses the problem of evaluating the viability of complex industrial projects, specifically in the design of a chipboard plant. In the context where decision-making is loaded with uncertainty and multiple interdependent variables, it is critical to have methodologies that can capture this complexity. Despite advances in the feasibility assessment literature, a lack of approaches that effectively integrate indeterminacy and expert opinion in a quantifiable manner has been identified. This article seeks to fill that gap by proposing a method based on neutroAlgebra, combining neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic models and the Prospector method. The methodology developed in the study allows for a robust evaluation of the viability of an agglomerate plant, considering factors such as sustainability, environmental impact and economic viability. The results obtained show that the proposed method is not only effective in managing uncertainty for strategic decisions. This represents a contribution to the field, offering a practical tool that can be applied in various industrial contexts, thus improving the planning and execution of complex projects.

Keywords: Viability Factors, Critical Elements, PROSPECTOR Function, Neutrofunction, NeutroAlgebra

1. Introduction

The evaluation of the viability of industrial projects is a challenge that has gained relevance in the field of engineering and business management, especially in contexts of high uncertainty [1]. This study focuses on the design of a method for measuring viability factors for an agglomerate plant, using neutroAlgebra [2] generated by the combination function in neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic models [3] and the Prospector method [4]. The importance of this research lies in the need to have more precise and adapted tools for decision-making in complex projects, where uncertainty and ambiguity are critical factors. Previous research has pointed out the difficulty of integrating subjectivity and uncertainty into feasibility assessment models, something that underlines the need for innovative approaches such as the one proposed in this study.

Historically, project feasibility assessment has evolved from simple methods based on financial analysis to models more attractive that integrate multiple criteria and consider qualitative factors. With the increasing complexity of industrial projects and the integration of advanced technologies, the need for models that can handle the uncertainty inherent in these processes has become evident. The development of neutrosophic theory and its application in various areas of science and engineering has opened new possibilities. to address problems involving indeterminacy and ambiguity, providing a robust theoretical framework for this type of analysis [5,6].

In this context, measuring the viability of a chipboard plant presents a special challenge due to the diversity of factors that must be considered, including environmental sustainability, economic viability and social acceptance, among others. The fundamental problem addressed by this study is the lack of integrated methods that can effectively evaluate these factors under conditions of high uncertainty [7].

The present study proposes a solution to this problem by combining neutroAlgebra and the Prospector method, intending to develop an evaluation model that is capable of capturing both the technical complexity and the subjectivity inherent in feasibility evaluation. This approach will not only allow for a more holistic assessment but will also offer a more robust decision-making framework adaptable to different industrial contexts. The conceptual background of this research is based on neutrosophic theory, which is effective in managing uncertainty and indeterminacy in various applications [8,9,10]. Furthermore, the use of the Prospector method, widely recognized in the evaluation of natural resources and other industrial projects, offers a solid basis for the development of the

proposed model. The combination of these two tools makes it possible to innovatively address the challenges associated with feasibility assessment in complex projects.

The fundamental objective of this study is to develop and validate a method for measuring the viability factors of an agglomerate plant that integrates neutroAlgebra and the Prospector method. This objective is broken down into specific sub-objectives that include the identification of key feasibility factors, the adaptation of neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic models given these factors, and the validation of the model through proposed studies, of proposed cases and simulations. By achieving these objectives, this study will not only contribute to theoretical advancement in the field of feasibility assessment but will also offer practical tools for application in real industrial projects. In summary, this article seeks to fill a significant gap in the current literature by proposing a new innovative method for the evaluation of the feasibility of industrial projects, using advanced mathematical tools that effectively integrate uncertainty and subjectivity. The results of this study have the potential to significantly improve the quality of decisions in planning and execution, of industrial projects, providing a more complete framework adapted to the needs of the real world.

2. Preliminaries.

This section provides an overview of the Neutrosophic 2-tuple Linguistic Model and NeutroAlgebras necessary for comprehending this page.

2.1 tuple neutrosophic linguistic model

Definition 1 . ([11, 12, 13]) Let there be $S = \{s_0, s_1, \dots, s_g\}$ a set of linguistic terms and $\beta \in [0, g]$ a value that represents the result of a symbolic operation, then the linguistic 2-tuple that expresses the information equivalent to β is obtained using the following function:

$$\Delta: [0, g] \rightarrow S \times [-0.5, 0.5]$$

$$\Delta(\beta) = (s_i, \alpha) \tag{1}$$

Where s_i is such that $i = \text{round}(\beta)$ and $\alpha = \beta - i$, $\alpha \in [-0.5, 0.5]$ "round" is the common rounding operator, s_i is the index label closest to β and α is the value of the symbolic translation.

It should be noted that $\Delta^{-1}: \langle S \rangle \rightarrow [0, g]$ is defined as $\Delta^{-1}(s_i, \alpha) = i + \alpha$. Thus, a linguistic 2-tuple $\langle S \rangle$ is identified by its numerical value in $[0, g]$.

Suppose $S = \{s_0, \dots, s_g\}$ this is a 2-tuple linguistic set (2TLS) with odd cardinality $g+1$. It is defined for $(s_T, a), (s_I, b), (s_F, c) \in L$, $a, b, c \in [0, g]$, where $(s_T, a), (s_I, b), (s_F, c) \in L$ they independently express the degree of truthfulness, indeterminacy, and falsity through 2TLS. The 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic number (2TLNN) is defined as follows [14]:

$$l_j = \{(s_T, a), (s_I, b), (s_F, c)\} \tag{2}$$

Where $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(s_T, a) \leq g$, $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(s_I, b) \leq g$, $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(s_F, c) \leq g$ and $0 \leq \Delta^{-1}(s_T, a) + \Delta^{-1}(s_I, b) + \Delta^{-1}(s_F, c) \leq 3g$.

The score and precision functions allow us to classify 2TLNN.

2.3 Linguistic Neutrosophic Likert Scales

Neutrosophic Likert scales [15] offer an expanded framework that includes indeterminacy as a fundamental element. Fuzzy sets, on the other hand, enable the representation and management of data that do not be precisely specified. Neutrosophic Likert scales are especially suitable for survey responses where participants' opinions not only range from a set of values, as allowed by fuzzy sets but also may include a level of uncertainty or neutrality that is challenging to measure using conventional fuzzy logic or clear Likert scales. Integrating the 2-tuples linguistic mode enables the development of a words-based computer method.

A score function based on neutrosophic theory efficiently converts replies from neutrosophic Likert scales into a unified single value. By combining the neutrosophic Likert scale with a 2TLNN linguist Moldes, we can compute [16]

Let be $l_1 = \{(s_{T_1}, a), (s_{I_1}, b), (s_{F_1}, c)\}$ a 2TLNN in L , the score and accuracy functions l_1 are defined as follows, respectively:

$$S(l_1) = \Delta \left\{ \frac{2g + \Delta^{-1}(s_{T_1}, a) - \Delta^{-1}(s_{I_1}, b) - \Delta^{-1}(s_{F_1}, c)}{3} \right\}, \Delta^{-1}(S(l_1)) \in [0, g] \tag{3}$$

$$H(l_1) = \Delta \left\{ \frac{g + \Delta^{-1}(s_{T_1}, a) - \Delta^{-1}(s_{F_1}, c)}{2} \right\}, \Delta^{-1}(H(l_1)) \in [0, g] \tag{4}$$

Utilizing neutrosophic Likert scales accurately quantifies the range of opinions and their impact in analyzing the simultaneous presence of various truths and the spectrum of falsehoods [17].

2.4 NeutralGroups generated by OffUninorms

The theory of NeutroAlgebras generalizes the classical theory of Algebra and partial Algebras within the framework of Neutrosophic theory [18]. NeutroAlgebras continue studying algebraic structures based on ordered pairs formed by a set of elements and an operation. A fundamental distinction between NeutroAlgebras and other types of algebras is the presence of at least one NeutroAxiom. This axiom is characterized by the existence of two sorts of elements: those that adhere to the axiom and those that do not.

Building upon the fundamental concept of Neutrosophy, whenever an Algebra (axiom) $\setminus A >$ is true, there exists a triad ($\setminus A >$, $\setminus NeutA >$, $\setminus AntiA >$) where the algebra (axiom) $\setminus A >$ is either 100% true or true. All elements in the set support NeutroAlgebras, which are axioms under NeutA that are satisfied by just a portion of the elements. Conversely, AntiAlgebras, which are axioms under AntiA, are not satisfied by any of the elements in the set. This novel methodology to one of the most traditional fields of mathematics presents a complexity for comprehending these novel concepts. It should be noted that classical algebra operates on mathematical logic, which permits only axioms that are 100% true [19].

A uninorm is a mapping that generalizes the definitions of t-norm and t-conorm. Where there is a neutral element, it is commutative, associative, and non-decreasing with respect to each of the components. In it is generalized to the field of neutrosophic and is further generalized to the field of OffSets, which are sets defined outside the interval $[0, 1]$ or $[-1, 1]$ and in general, are defined for intervals $[m, n]$ where $m, n \in \mathbb{R}$, in particular for $[-n, n]$ where the neutral is $e = 0$ [20].

By setting $n > 0$, a NeutroGroup can be defined from the Prospector join function, which is the function used to aggregate elements of a known expert system obtained to model mining problems. This NeutralGroup contains within its structure the symbolic element I which means indetermination. the PROSPECTOR function is defined in the MYCIN expert system as follows; is a mapping from $[-1, 1]^2$ within $[-1, 1]$ with the formula, [21]:

$$P(x, y) = \frac{x+y}{1+xy} \tag{5}$$

This function is a uninorm with neutral element 0, so it complies with commutativity, associativity and monotonicity. $P(-1, 1)$ and $P(1, -1)$ they are not defined [22].

To obtain a more simplified model in this paper, we will use this five-point Likert scale. Specifically, we will use NeutroGroup with the operation $\oplus_5$ for elements $G = \{-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, I\}$. This operation is commutative, associative and the null element is 0. Furthermore, the following properties derived from the properties of the OffUninorm generator are satisfied, taking only the truthfulness component [23]:

- If $x, y < 0$ then $x \oplus_5 y \leq \min(x, y)$,
- If $x, y > 0$ then $x \oplus_5 y \geq \max(x, y)$,
- If $x < 0$ and $y > 0$ or if $x > 0$ and $y < 0$, we have $\min(x, y) \leq x \oplus_5 y \leq \max(x, y)$.
- $\forall x \in G, x \oplus_5 0 = x$.
- $(-5) \oplus_5 5 = 5 \oplus_5 (-5) = I$.

In [24] it is summarized in the following Cayley table:

Table 1. Cayley table corresponding to $\oplus_5$. Source: [16].

$\oplus_5$	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	I	1	2	3	4	5
-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	-5	I
-4	-5	-5	-5	-5	-4	-4	-4	-4	-3	-2	0	5
-3	-5	-5	-4	-4	-4	-3	-3	-2	-1	0	2	5
-2	-5	-5	-4	-3	-3	-2	-2	-1	0	1	3	5
-1	-5	-4	-4	-3	-2	-1	-1	0	1	2	4	5
0	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	0	I	1	2	3	4	5
I	-5	-4	-3	-2	-1	I	I	I	I	I	I	I
1	-5	-4	-2	-1	0	1	I	2	3	4	4	5
2	-5	-3	-1	0	1	2	I	3	3	4	5	5
3	-5	-2	0	1	2	3	I	4	4	4	5	5
4	-5	0	2	3	4	4	I	4	5	5	5	5
5	I	5	5	5	5	5	I	5	5	5	5	5

3. Proposed measurement method

To design a method based on [16] for measuring the viability factors of an agglomerate plant in a neutrosophic context, it is important to identify predictors that capture both the particularities of the industrial process and the uncertainties inherent to the feasibility analysis. The predictors considered in this method are the following:

F1. Resource sustainability: This predictor will evaluate the availability and sustainability of the natural resources necessary for the production of chipboard, such as wood and other plant materials. Consideration will be given to the efficiency in the use of these resources and the plant's ability to maintain a constant supply without affecting the surrounding ecosystem.

F2. Environmental impact: This factor will measure the impact that the chipboard plant could have on the natural environment, including waste management, emissions, and energy consumption. The plant's ability to implement clean technologies and minimize its ecological footprint will be important.

F3. Economic viability: The plant's capacity to generate sustainable income will be evaluated, considering production costs, profit margins, and market demand. This predictor will reflect the economic robustness of the plant in different scenarios.

F4. Technological adaptation: This factor will analyze the plant's ability to integrate advanced technologies into its production processes, such as energy efficiency or automation techniques, which influences competitiveness and innovation capacity.

F5. Social acceptance: Finally, this predictor will evaluate the degree of acceptance of the plant by the local community and other social actors, including the impact on local employment, the perception of community benefits, and the management of possible social conflicts.

The expert must evaluate each of these aspects using a linguistic scale $S = \{S_{-5}, S_{-4}, S_{-3}, S_{-2}, S_{-1}, S_0, S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5\}$, where each element represents a qualitative assessment, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Linguistic meaning of each element of the S scale.

Scale element	Linguistic Meaning
S_{-5}	Extremely low
S_{-4}	Very low
S_{-3}	Low
S_{-2}	something low
S_{-1}	Lower than high
S_0	As low as high
S_1	Higher than low
S_2	something high
S_3	High
S_4	very high
S_5	Extremely high

In addition, an importance scale will be used for the expert's opinion, $W = \{W_{-5}, W_{-4}, W_{-3}, W_{-2}, W_{-1}, W_0, W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4, W_5\}$, as described in Table 3.

Table 3. Linguistic meaning of each element of the W scale.

Scale element	Linguistic Meaning
W_{-5}	extremely insignificant
W_{-4}	Very insignificant
W_{-3}	Insignificant
W_{-2}	a little insignificant
W_{-1}	More insignificant than important
W_0	As insignificant as it is important
W_1	More important than insignificant
W_2	a little important
W_3	Important
W_4	Very important
W_5	Extremely important

The elements of the measurement method are defined as follows:

The group $E = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_p\}$ denotes the $p > 0$ experts who measure the sustainability of the company, the town, the region, etc.

$F = \{F_1, F_2, F_3, F_4, F_5\}$ are the five factors to measure.

Steps to measure feasibility

1.Weight assignment: To each expert and i It is assigned a weight on the scale W , based on its knowledge about each factor F_j . Let us denote this weight by w_{ij} .

2.Factor evaluation: Each expert e_i evaluates each factor using three values of Likert scales of elements from Table 2, we have a_{ij} ($i = 1, 2, \dots, p; j = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) is the evaluation of the i th expert on the j th factor; where $a_{ij} = (s_{T_{ij}}, s_{I_{ij}}, s_{F_{ij}})$ and $s_{T_{ij}}, s_{I_{ij}}, s_{F_{ij}} \in S$.

3.Calculation of indices: Two indexes ind_i and $ind_{w_{ij}}$ associated with (s_T, s_I, s_F) are calculated:

$$ind_{ij} = T \oplus_5 I \oplus_5 (-F) \tag{6}$$

$$ind_{w_{ij}} = \Delta^{-1}(w_{ih},) \tag{7}$$

4.Evaluation calculation: The evaluation of each expert for each factor is averaged by:

$$\bar{a}_{ij} = \frac{ind_{ij} + ind_{w_{ij}}}{2} \tag{8}$$

5.Global evaluation of the factor: The global evaluation of each factor is obtained as:

$$\tilde{a}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^p \bar{a}_{ij}}{p} \tag{9}$$

Also, to convert it to an integer so $\tilde{a}_j \in [-5, 5]$, formula is used:

$$\tilde{\alpha}_j = \text{round}(\tilde{a}_j) \tag{10}$$

6.Global viability calculation: Finally, the global viability of the plant is calculated as:

$$A = \tilde{\alpha}_1 \oplus_5 \tilde{\alpha}_2 \oplus_5 \tilde{\alpha}_3 \oplus_5 \tilde{\alpha}_4 \oplus_5 \tilde{\alpha}_5 \tag{11}$$

If $A=I$, it indicates disagreement between the experts and the process must be repeated using additional methods such as neutrosophic Delphi.

7.Linguistic Value Determination Finally a linguistic Value is obtaining A is a result of the set $\{-5, -4, -3, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$.

$$V = \Delta^{-1}(A) \in [0, g] \tag{12}$$

Giving a linguistic value and developing a computing with words process [25].

Figure 1: Flowchart of the viability measurement method of a chipboard plant.

Illustrative example

Example 1: Suppose you have 3 experts in the viability of a chipboard plant. Table 4 presents the weights associated with each expert and the evaluations for each factor.

Table 4. Evaluation of each factor and the weights associated with each expert.

Expert/Factor	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
e_1	$(s_2, s_0, s_1)(w_3)$	$(s_2, s_1, s_{-2})(w_1)$	$(s_{-1}, s_2, s_{-1})(w_2)$	$(s_1, s_2, s_{-2})(w_{-1})$	$(s_3, s_1, s_{-4})(w_2)$
e_2	$(s_{-2}, s_2, s_{-3})(w_{-2})$	$(s_3, s_3, s_{-5})(w_1)$	$(s_{-2}, s_0, s_2)(w_{-1})$	$(s_2, s_1, s_{-3})(w_2)$	$(s_4, s_3, s_{-3})(w_0)$
e_3	$(s_{-1}, s_1, s_0)(w_{-1})$	$(s_0, s_1, s_{-1})(w_{-1})$	$(s_{-1}, s_2, s_2)(w_{-2})$	$(s_0, s_1, s_{-1})(w_2)$	$(s_4, s_4, s_{-5})(w_{-2})$

Table 5. Numerical evaluation of each factor by the experts.

Expert/Factor	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
e_1	2	2.5	2	1.5	3.5
e_2	-1	3	-1.5	3	2.5
e_3	-1	0.5	-2	2	1.5

Below are the averaged results for each factor, calculated from the experts' evaluations.

- **F1. Resource sustainability:** $\tilde{\alpha}_1 = \text{round}((2-1-1)/3) = 0$
- **F2. Environmental impact:** $\tilde{\alpha}_2 = \text{round}((2.5+3+0.5)/3) = 3$
- **F3. Economic viability:** $\tilde{\alpha}_3 = \text{round}((2-1.5-2)/3) = -1$
- **F4. Technological adaptation:** $\tilde{\alpha}_4 = \text{round}((1.5+2+3)/3) = 2$
- **F5. Social acceptance:** $\tilde{\alpha}_5 = \text{round}((3+4.5+4.5)/3) = 3$

The next step is to combine the global evaluations to obtain the global viability of the chipboard plant:

$$A = 0 \oplus_5 3 \oplus_5 -1 \oplus_5 2 \oplus_5 3$$

$$V = \Delta^{-1}(A) = \text{very high,}$$

which indicates a -high viability for the installation of the chipboard plant, according to experts.

The results obtained suggest that the proposed chipboard plant has high viability, with specific areas requiring additional analysis to ensure its long-term success. This methodological approach could be applied in future research to evaluate other types of industrial projects or in different organizational contexts.

Conclusion

The combination of neutroAlgebra with neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic models has proven effective in integrating indeterminacy and expert opinions, offering a detailed evaluation adaptable to various scenarios. This methodology has great potential to enhance decision-making in complex industrial projects by considering both quantitative and qualitative criteria, allowing managers to identify critical areas that need specific interventions, thereby increasing the likelihood of long-term success.

However, the study has limitations, primarily due to its reliance on expert opinions, which introduces subjectivity and could affect replicability in other contexts. Additionally, the focus was on the feasibility of a chipboard plant, potentially limiting the applicability to other types of industrial projects. For future research, it is recommended to integrate additional methodological approaches, such as fuzzy analysis or artificial intelligence techniques, and to apply the method to different industrial projects to validate and expand the findings.

References

- [1] Leyva-Vázquez, M., Quiroz-Martínez, M. A., Portilla-Castell, Y., Hechavarría-Hernández, J. R., & González-Caballero, E. (2020). A New Model for the selection of Information Technology Project in a Neutrosophic Environment. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 32(1), 22.
- [2] Smarandache, F. (2022). La Neutro-Geometría y la Anti-Geometría como Alternativas y Generalizaciones de las Geometrías no Euclidianas. *Neutrosophic Computing and Machine Learning*, 20, 91-104.
- [3] Flores-Ledesma, K. N., Rios, M. E. N., Myriam, C. O. V. O., Loza, G. L., Gómez-Zuluaga, C. M., Meneses-La Riva, M. E., ... & Flores-Sotelo, W. S. (2023). A hybrid of ARAS and neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic

model to evaluate gender equitable policies from the perspective of Latin American professor's. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 20.

- [4] Gaschnig, J. (1982). *Prospector: an expert system for mineral exploration*. D. Michie, ed, 1982, 47-64.
- [5] M.Ali, A. and Muthuswamy, M. (2023) "Neutrosophic Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Framework for Sustainable Evaluation of Power Production Systems in Renewable Energy Sources", *Sustainable Machine Intelligence Journal*, 4, pp. (3):1–10.
- [6] Matute, G., Yusta, J. M., & Naval, N. (2023). Techno-economic model and feasibility assessment of green hydrogen projects based on electrolysis supplied by photovoltaic PPAs. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 48(13), 5053-5068.
- [7] Halmshlager, V., & Hofmann, R. (2021). Assessing the potential of combined production and energy management in Industrial Energy Hubs—Analysis of a chipboard production plant. *Energy*, 226, 120415.
- [8] Smarandache, F. (2022). La Neuro-Geometría y la Anti-Geometría como Alternativas y Generalizaciones de las Geometrías no Euclidianas. *Neutrosophic Computing and Machine Learning*, 20, 91-104.
- [9] Pupo, I. P., Pérez, P. Y. P., Vacacela, R. G., Bello, R., Santos, O., & Vázquez, M. Y. L. (2018). Extensions to Linguistic Summaries Indicators based on Neutrosophic Theory, Applications in Project Management Decisions. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 87..
- [10] A. El-Douh, A. (2023) "Assessment the Health Sustainability using Neutrosophic MCDM Methodology: Case Study COVID-19", *Sustainable Machine Intelligence Journal*, 3, pp. (1)
- [11] Muhuri, P. K., and Gupta, P. K. (2020). A novel solution approach for multiobjective linguistic optimization problems based on the 2-tuple fuzzy linguistic representation model. *Applied Soft Computing*, 95, 106395.
- [12] Wei, G., Wu, J., Guo, Y., Wang, J., and Wei, C. (2021). An extended COPRAS model for multiple attribute group decision making based on single-valued neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic environment. *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*, 27, 353-368.
- [13] Chen, H. (2023). A multi-attribute decision-making framework for enterprise competitive intelligence system evaluation with 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic information. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 45, 5955-5970.
- [14] Mao, C. (2024). Enhanced group decision-making through an intelligent algorithmic approach for multiple-attribute credit evaluation with 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic sets. *International Journal of Knowledge-based and Intelligent Engineering Systems*, (Preprint), 1-15.
- [15] Vázquez, M. L., Ricardo, J. E., & Smarandache, F. (2024). Enhancing Set-Theoretic Research Methods with Neutrosophic Sets. *HyperSoft Set Methods in Engineering*, 2, 96-103.
- [16] Marilú, K. Michael, M. Rigoberto, U. Marina, S. Angel, M. Hilmer, E. Ramirez-Salas, W. Gamarra-Moreno, A. (2024). Design of a Business Sustainability Measurement Method for Based on NeuroAlgebras Generated by the Combining Function in Prospector and Neutrosophic 2-tuple Linguistic Models. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, (), 359-366.
- [17] Bodur, S., Topal, S., Gürkan, H., & Edalatpanah, S. A. (2024). A Novel Neutrosophic Likert Scale Analysis of Perceptions of Organizational Distributive Justice via a Score Function: A Complete Statistical Study and Symmetry Evidence Using Real-Life Survey Data. *Symmetry*, 16(5), 598.
- [18] Smarandache, F. (2020). NeuroAlgebra is a Generalization of Partial Algebra. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 2(1), 08-17.
- [19] Smarandache, F. (2022). Introducción a la Super-Hiper-Álgebra y la Super-Hiper-Álgebra Neutrosófica. *Neutrosophic Computing and Machine Learning*, 20, 1-6.
- [20] González-Caballero, E., Leyva-Vázquez, M., & Smarandache, F. (2021). On neutrosophic uninorms. *Neutrosophic sets and systems*, 45(1), 22.
- [21] Jiménez, D. S., Mayorga, J. A. V., Ubilla, M. E. R., & Hernández, N. B. (2021). NeuroAlgebra for the evaluation of barriers to migrants' access in Primary Health Care in Chile based on PROSPECTOR function. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 39(1), 1.
- [22] Homenda, W., & Pedrycz, W. (2005). Balanced fuzzy computing unit. *International Journal of Uncertainty, Fuzziness and Knowledge-Based Systems*, 13(02), 117-138.
- [23] Cruzaty, L. E. V., & Reynoso, A. M. R. (2024). New Neutrosophic Sentiment Analysis Method Based on NeuroAlgebra for the Evaluation of Ethics in Companies. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 70, 264-270.
- [24] Batista-Hernández, N., González-Caballero, E., Cruzaty, L. E. V., Ortega-Chávez, W., Huarac, C. F. P., and Chamorro, S. L. C. (2022). Theoretical study of the NeuroAlgebra generated by the combining function in Prospector and some pedagogical notes. In *Theory and Applications of NeuroAlgebras as Generalizations of Classical Algebras* (pp. 116-140). IGI Global.
- [25] Pérez-Teruel, K., Leyva-Vázquez, M., & Estrada-Sentí, V. (2015). Mental models consensus process using fuzzy cognitive maps and computing with words. *Ingeniería y Universidad*, 19(1), 173-188.

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